

A REVIEW ON MEDICINAL PLANTS FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF OSTEOPOROSIS

G. Mahalakshmi^{1*}, T. Nirmala², R. Samundeswari³, D. Sivassoupramanien⁴ and S. Kavimani⁵

¹⁻⁵ Department of Pharmacology, Mother Theresa Post Graduate And Research Institute of Health And Sciences, Puducherry – 605006, Tamil Nadu, India

E-mail: mahamaya2603@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

From ancient times many medicinal herbs have been reported in literature to treat osteoporosis. Natural Products are also a part of our everyday life. Right from the inception, India has a rich heritage of usage of Ayurvedic & Herbal medicines Herbal have just recently started rising on the horizon of alternative system of medicine. Ayurveda and Herbal were being practiced and used all over the world for many years but have only recently started getting legal acceptance in many countries in the world as alternative system of medicine. India is called “Botanical Garden of the world” as it is the largest producer of medicinal herbs. Out of more than 25000 plants of medicinal value, only 10 % are used for their medicinal value. Around 1800 species are systematically documented in the codified Indian systems of medicine. These herbal products are preventive, protective, nutritive and curative. This Review is made to list out the Medicinal plants, which have been reported to have Anti osteoporotic activity against various animal models.

Key words: Osteoporosis, Medicinal plants, Ovariectomized rat model, Glucocorticoid induced Osteoporosis and in vitro methods.

INTRODUCTION

Osteoporosis, a silent epidemic has become a major health hazard in recent years. It is a major growing health problem for elderly women associated with ovarian hormone deficiency following menopause and is by and far the most common cause of age related bone loss in women. According to the WHO “Osteoporosis is a disease characterized by low bone mass and microarchitectural deterioration of bone tissues, leading to enhanced fragility and consequent increase in fracture risk that results in fractures with minimal trauma”.

There is imbalance between bone formation (osteoblastic activity) and bone resorption process (osteoclastic activity) due to various causes such as deficiency of estrogen hormone

as in post menopausal osteoporosis, aging and oxidative stress.

As a living tissue, bone is always in state of remodeling. This process replaces old and weak bone tissue by fresh and hard bone tissue. Following types of cells govern the process of remodeling.

- (1) Osteoclast that resorbs the bone matrix and degrades the bone tissue by synthesizing digestive enzymes.
- (2) Osteoblast that forms the bone tissue by synthesizing collagen matrix, which become hardened by process of calcification.
- (3) Osteocytes are found embedded into the collagen matrix. When osteoblasts become trapped in the matrix they secrete, they become osteocytes.

Remodeling occurs as a delicate balance between bone resorption by osteoclasts and bone formation by osteoblasts. Imbalance between the activities of these cells leads to various diseased conditions (Yan Zhang et al., 2007).

Herbal medicines are being used by about 80% of the world population primarily in the developing countries for primary health care. They have stood the test of time for their safety, efficacy, cultural acceptability and lesser side effects.

Table-1: Medicinal Plants With their Botanical Name and Chemical Constituents for Osteoporosis

Sl. NO	Common Name	Biological Name & Family	Chemical Constituent	Effective against	Reference
1.	Ox nee	<i>Achyranthusbidentata</i> (Amaranthaceae)	rutin, saponins, achyranthine, caffeic acid, oleanolic acid, inokosterone, ecdysterone, rubrosterone	Ovariectomized rat model	Rong et al., 2011
2.	Bui	<i>Allophylusserratus</i> (Sapindaceae)	Flavonoids, tannins, Fatty acids	In vitro chick fetal bone assay	Manmeet k et al., 2010
3.	Leek	<i>Allium porrum</i> (Amaryllidaceae)	diallyl disulfide, diallyl trisulfide, diallyl tetrasulfide), flavonoids, vitamin C, and carotenoids	Ethanol induced osteoporosis	Siham M. et al., 2013
4.	Jewel orchids	<i>Anoectochilusformosanus</i> (Orchidaceae)	Kinsenoside, Flavonoids	Ovariectomized rat model	Shih CC et al., 2001
5.	Haung qi	<i>Astragalusmembranaceous</i> (Fabaceae)	Cycloastragenol, Triterpenoids, Isoflavone	Ovariectomized rat model	LiuXP et al., 2005
6.	Sappanligum	<i>Caesalpiniasappan</i> (Fabaceae)	Triterpenoids, flavonoids, oxygen heterocycles, Brazilin	In vitro osteoblast cell proliferation	Subehan et al., 2013
7.	Safflower	<i>Carthamustinctorius</i> (Asteraceae)	Flavonoids, Fixed oil, Kinobean A	Ovariectomized rat model	Alam et al., 2006
8.	Tea	<i>Camellia sinensis</i> (Theaceae)	Polyphenols and flavonoids	Ovariectomized rat model	Das et al., 2004
9.	Foetid bugbane	<i>Cimciferrafoetida</i> (Ranunculaceae)	Cimcifoetisides a & B, Triterpenoids	Ovariectomized rat model	Li et al., 2005
10.	Black cohosh	<i>Cimciferaracemosa</i> (Ranunculaceae)	Flavonoids, Triterpenoids, glycosides and aromatic acids	Ovariectomized rat model	Nisslein T et al., 2003
11.	Hadjod	<i>Cissusquadrangularis</i> (Vitaceae)	Steroids, Alkaloids, Calcium	Ovariectomized rat model	Shirwaike r et al., 2003
12.	Guggul	<i>Commiphoramukul</i> (Burseraceae)	guggulsterones E and Z, guggulsterol-I, II, III, cholesterol, sesamin and camphorene.	Ovariectomized rat model	Saleemull a k et al., 2012
13.	Dogwoods	<i>Cornusofficinalis</i> (Cornaceae)	Oleanic acid, ursolic acid, gallotannins	Ovariectomized rat model	Chen et al., 2003
14.	Turmeric	<i>Curcuma aromatica</i> (Zingiberaceae)	curdione, neocurdione, curcumol, tetramethylpyrazine, 9-oxo-neoprocumamol, curcumin	Ovariectomized rat model	Rangrez et al., 2011
15.	Purple yam	Dioscoreaalata	1- feruloglycerol, anthocyanins, diosgenin, tocopherol, ipomeanol, sinapic acid.	Ovariectomized rat model	Hsiao LC et al., 2008

S. N.	Common Name	Biological Name & Family	Chemical Constituent	Effective against	Reference
16.	Basket ferns	<i>Drynariaerhizome</i> (Polypodiaceae)	Phloroglucinol, chlorogenic acid, syringic acid, quercetin dehydrate, luteolin and emodin	In vitro osteoblast cell proliferation	Suk NK et al., 2014
17.	Siberian Ginseng	<i>Eleutherococcus senticosus</i> (Araliaceae)	Amyloid β (A β), and eleutheroside B	Ovariectomized rat model	Dong WL et al., 2013
18.	Amla	<i>Emblica officinalis</i> (Phyllanthaceae)	Flavone, gallic acid, ellagic acid, linolenic, linoleic, oleic, stearic acids.	Ovariectomized rat model	Srinivasa R et al., 2013
19.	Herbaepimedi	<i>Epimedium breucorium</i> (Berberidaceae)	Flavonoids, sterols, fatty acids	Ovariectomized rat model	Xie F et al., 2005
20.	Indian coral tree	<i>Erythrina variegata</i> (Leguminosae)	Isoflavonoids, sphaerobioside, dorientanol B	Ovariectomized rat model	Wong et al., 2007
21.	Tongkatali	<i>Eurycomalongifolia</i> (Simaroubaceae)	Eurycomanone, eurycomalactone	Orchidectomy rat model	Nadia ME et al., 2012
22.	Glossy Privet Fruit	<i>Fructus ligustri</i> (Oleaceae)	<u>Oleanolic acid, luteoline, D-glucoside, quercitrin, sitosterol</u>	Ovariectomized rat model	Ko et al., 2010
23.	Soy bean	<i>Glycine max</i> (Fabaceae)	Isoflavonoids, genistein, daidzein	Human adult	Potter et al., 1998.
24.	Maca	<i>Lepidium meyenii</i> (Brassicaceae)	Alkaloids, steroids, macamides	Ovariectomized rat model	Yong zhong et al., 2006
25.	Cheese fruit	<i>Morinda citrifolia</i> (Rubiaceae)	americanin A, narcissoside, asperuloside, asperulosidic acid, borrieriagenin, citrifolinin B	Ovariectomized rat model	Shirwaiker et al., 2011
26.	Indian mulberry	<i>Morinda officinalis</i> (Rubiaceae)	Morindin, vitamin C, Anthroquinones, terpenoids	Ovariectomized rat model	Nan li et al., 2009
27.	Drumstick tree	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> (Moringaceae)	pterygospermin, moringine, moringininespirochin, behenic acid, moringic acid, niazinin A & B, niazimicin, steroids.	In vitro osteoblastic cell proliferation	Chirag P et al., 2013
28.	Fennel flower	<i>Nigella sativa</i> (Ranunculaceae)	n-nonane, dihydrocarvone, citronellyl acetate, aromadendrene, davanone, 8-heptadecene, dihydrofarnesyl acetate and pimaradiene	Diabetes induced osteoporosis in female rats	Rukshar A et al., 2013
29.	Onobrychis	<i>Onobrychis ebenoids</i> (Leguminosae)	Arylobenzofurans and isoflavonoids	Ovariectomized rat model	Dontas et al., 2006
30.	Ginseng	<i>Panax ginseng</i> (Araliaceae)	Ginsenosides, polysaccharides, polyacetylenes, peptides, and amino acids	Inflammation induced osteoporosis in ovariectomized rat model	Avsar U et al., 2013
31.	Chaphlu	<i>Piper sarmentosum</i> (Piperaceae)	Ellitorine, guineensine, brachystamide B, sarmentine, brachyamide	Glucocorticoid induced osteoporosis in adrenalectomized rats	Ima NS et al., 2012
32.	Mushroom	<i>Pleurotus eryngii</i> (Pleurotaceae)	Polysaccharides, voluatoxin, gonaderic acid	Ovariectomized rat model	Kim et al., 2006
33.	False Ashoka	<i>Polyalthia longifolia</i> (Annonaceae)	Steroids, flavonoids, alkaloids, phenols, tannins	Dexamethasone induced osteoporosis in rats	Pawar et al., 2012

S. N.	Common Name	Biological Name & Family	Chemical Constituent	Effective against	Reference
34.	Bawachi	<i>Psoralea corylifolia</i> (Fabaceae)	Furanocoumarins, flavonoids (<u>neobavaisoflavone</u> , <u>isobavachalcone</u> , <u>bavachalcone</u> , <u>bavachinin</u> , <u>bavachin</u>), terpenoids	Ovariectomized rat model	Tsai MH et al., 2007
35.	Soft bollygum	<i>Litsea Glutinosa</i> (Lauraceae)	Oleic acid, tricosene, Eicosane, phytoestrogens	Ovariectomized rat model	Rangrez et al., 2011
36.	Ge gen	<i>Puerariaeradix</i> (Leguminosae)	Isoflavone, daidzin, daidzein	Ovariectomized mice model	Wang XX et al., 2003
37.	Pomegranate	<i>Punicagranatum</i> (Lythraceae)	Ellagic acid, Gallic acid, punicalin, punicalagin	Ovariectomized rat model	Mori et al., 2004
38.	Skullcaps	<i>Radixscutellarie</i> (Lamiaceae)	Flavonoids, baicalein, wogonin, wogonoside	Density and Microarchitecture of long bones in Tail Suspended rat model	Chen RL et al., 2013
39.	Chinese foxglove	<i>Rehmanniaglutinosa</i> (Scrophulariaceae)	Steroids, nancarotenoids, remophilanetriol	Ovariectomized rat model	Oh et al., 2003
40.	Indian madder	<i>Rubiaccordifolia</i> (Rubiaceae)	Rubiadin, anthroquinones, flavonoids, rubiprasins, triterpenoids	Ovariectomized rat model	Kasaki et al., 2012
41.	Red sage	<i>Salviamiltorrhiza</i> (Lamiaceae)	Dihydrotanshinone, tashinone I and II A	Ovariectomized rat model	Chae et al., 2004
42.	Black elder	<i>Sambucusnigra</i> (Caprofoliaceae)	α -amyrenone, α -amyrin, betulin, oleanolic acid, beta-sitosterol ¹² , nigrin b, a lectin similar to ricin	Diabetes induced osteoporosis in female rats	Laurentia B et al., 2012
43.	Jiegu mu	<i>Sambucuswilliamsii</i> (Caprofoliaceae)	Steroids, triterpenoids, phenolic acid	Ovariectomized rat model	Yao et al., 2005
44.	Stonecrops	<i>Sedumsarmentosum</i> (Crassulaceae)	Sedridine, sedamine, sedinone, isopelletierine	Ovariectomized rat model	Kim WH et al., 2004
45.	Japanese pagoda tree	<i>Sophorajaponica</i> (Leguminosae)	Isoflavonoids, triterpenoids	Ovariectomized rat model	Wang et al., 2006
46.	Arjuna	<i>Terminaliaarjuna</i> (Combretaceae)	Tannins, triterpenoids saponins (arjunic acid, arjunolic acid, arjungenin and arjunic acid), flavonoids, gallic acid, ellagic acid and phytosterols.	Ovariectomized rat model	Rangrez et al., 2011
47.	Red clover	<i>Trifoliumpratense</i> (Fabaceae)	Isoflavonoids like biochatmin-A and genistein	Ovariectomized rat model	Circosta et al., 2007
48.	Wheat	<i>Triticumaestivum</i> (Gramineae)	Vitamins (A, C, and E), Bioflavonoids, Iron, minerals (calcium and magnesium) and 17 amino acid	Glucocorticoid induced osteoporosis in rats	David B et al., 2013
49.	Pilabhangara	<i>Wedeliacalendaceae</i> (Asteraceae)	Isoflavonoids, wedelolactone	Ovariectomized rat model	Shirwaiker et al., 2003
50.	Ashwagandha	<i>Withaniasomnifera</i> (Apocynaceae)	Withanine, withananine, pseudo-withanine, tropine, pseudo-tropine, choline, cuscohygrine, isopelletierine, withanolides, withaferin A	Calcium deficient ovariectomized rat model	Prabhakara et al., 2010
51.	Ginger	<i>Zingiberofficinale</i> (Zingiberaceae)	Zingiberene, β - bisabolene, α -farnesne, β -sesquiphellandrene, α -curcumene, gingerol and shogao	Ovariectomized rat model	Mohamed LC et al., 2013

The chemical constituents present in them are a part of the physiological functions of living flora and hence they are believed to have better compatibility with the human body. Ancient literature also mentions herbal medicines for age related diseases namely memory loss, osteoporosis, diabetic wounds, immune and Liver disorders, etc. for which no modern medicine or only palliative therapy is available. These drugs are made from renewable resources of raw materials by ecofriendly processes and will bring economic prosperity to the masses growing these raw materials. (Reddy NP et al., 2004).

In this Review, an attempt is made to explore the possibility of using medicinal plants for the osteoporosis.

REFERENCES

1. Alam MR, Kim SM, Lee JI, *et al.* Effects of Safflower seed oil in osteoporosis induced-ovariectomized rats. *Am J Chin Med* 2006; 34: 601-12.
2. Ayaz Y, Rangrez, Suresh B and Pragna H. Parikh. Osteoprotective effect three anti-inflammatory plants in ovariectomized wistar rats. *Pharmacologyonline*, 2011; 1: 675-684.
3. Chae HJ, Chae SW, Yun DH, Keum KS, Yoo SK, Kim HR. Prevention of bone loss in ovariectomized rats: the effect of *Salvia miltiorrhiza* extracts. *Immunopharm Immunot*, 2004, 26 (1): 135-144.
4. Chen-RL, Guang-WZ, Yin-BN, Ya-LP, Yuan-KZ, Qi-BM. Antiosteoporosis Effect of Radix Scutellariae Extract on Density and Microstructure of Long Bones in Tail-Suspended Sprague-Dawley Rats. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, 2013; 2: 1-8.
5. Chen T. Effects of water drawing liquid of *Fructus corni* on bone morphology in osteoporosis mice. *Tianjin Pharmacy*, 2003, 15 (4): 5-6.
6. Chun Hay Ko, Wing SS, Ching PL, Clara BSL, Kwok PF, Ping CL. Osteoporotic effects of *fructus ligustri lucidiae* aqueous extract in aged ovariectomized rats. *Chines medicine* 2010; 5(39):1-9.
7. Chirag P, Ayaz R, Pragna P. The anti-Osteoporotic effect of *Moringa oleifera* on osteoblastic cells (SaOS2). *IOSR Journal of pharmacy and biological sciences*. 2013; 2:10-17.
8. Circosta C, Occhiuto F, Pasquale RD, *et al.* Effects of phytoestrogenic isoflavones from red clover (*Trifolium pratense* L.) on experimental osteoporosis. *Phytother Res* 2007; 21(2): 130-4.
9. Das AS, Mukherjee M, Mitra C. Evidence for a prospective anti-osteoporosis effect of black tea (*Camellia Sinensis*) extract in a bilaterally ovariectomized rat model. *Asia Pac J Clin Nutr* 2004; 13: 210-6.
10. David B, Otilia JF B, Vijaya LC, Saidulu A. Role of *Triticum aestivum* Aqueous extract in glucocorticoid-induced osteoporosis in rats. *Indian Journal of Experimental Biology*, 2014: 52: 153-158.
11. Dong WL, Jae GK, Youngseak L, Seok HC, Yun TK. Preventive effects of *Eleutherococcus senticosus* bark extract in OVX – induced osteoporosis in rats. *Molecules*, 2013; 1(8): 7998-8008.
12. Dontas I, Halabalaki M, Moutsatsou P, *et al.* Protective effect of plant extracts from *Onobrychis benoides* on ovariectomy-induced bone loss in rats. *Maturitas* 2006; 53: 234-42.
13. Hsiao LC, Ling TH, Jong KL, Ching JH. The bone-protective effect of a Taiwanese yam (*Dioscorea alata* L. cv. Tainung No. 2) in ovariectomized female BALB/C mice. *J Sci Food Agric*, 2009; 89: 517–522.

14. Ima NS, M.R Elvysuhana, M.A Siti, H.S. Farihah, A. Fairus, M.N. MuhamedAlfakari. *Piper sarmentosum* improves bone structure and biomechanical strength of rats given excess glucocorticoid. *British Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2012; 2(3): 168-187.
15. Kasaki S, Handral M, Prabu R. Evaluation of anti-osteoporotic activity of root extract *Rubiocordifolia* in ovariectomized rats. *International journal of drug development and research*, 2012;4(3):163-172.
16. Kim SW, Kim HG, Lee BE, *et al.* Effects of mushroom, *Pleurotuseryngii*, extracts on bone metabolism. *ClinNutr* 2006; 25: 166-70.
17. Kim WH, Park YJ, Park MR, Ha TY, Lee SH, Bae SJ, Kim M. Estrogenic effects of *Sedum sarmentosum* Bunge in ovariectomized rats. *J NutrSciVitaminol* (Tokyo), 2004, 50 (2):100-105.
18. Laurentiu B, Oana B, Magda B, Manuela C. Mechanism by *Sambucusnigra* Extract Improves Bone Mineral Density in Experimental Diabetes. *Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine*, Volume 2012: 1-8.
19. Li JX, Liu J, He CC, *et al.* Triterpenoids from *Cimicifugaerhizoma*, a novel class of inhibitors on bone resorption and ovariectomy-induced bone loss. *Maturitas* 2007; 58: 59-69.
20. Liu XP, Chen FL, Cheng YJ. Study of total isoflavone from *Astragalusmembranaceus* on the prevention of osteoporosis in rats. *Zhejiang JITCWM*, 2005, 15 (5): 282-283.
21. Manmeet K, Preeti R, Devendra M, AbhineshK, Gautam, Rashmi P, Divya S, Naibedya C, Rakesh M. Anti-osteoporotic constituents from Indian medicinal plants. *Phytomedicine* 2010; 13:993-999.
22. Mohamed S. M, Omayma M. M, Hoda H. Histological and morphometric effects of CdCl₂ and ginger on osteoporosis induced by bilateral ovariectomy in adult albino rats. *Eur. J. Anat*, 2013; 17 (2): 102-114.
23. Mori-Okamoto J, Otawara-Hamamoto Y, Yamato H, Yoshimura H. Pomegranate extract improves a depressive state and bone properties in menopausal syndrome model ovariectomized mice. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 2004, 92(1): 93-101.
24. Nadia ME, Norazlina M, Norliza M, Isainaina M, Ahmad NS. *Eurycomalongifolia*: Medicinal plant in the prevention and treatment of male osteoporosis due to androgen deficiency. *Evidence based complementary and Alternative medicine*, 2012. Volume 2012: 1-9.
25. Nan Li, Lu Ping Q, Ting H, Yan BW, Qiao YZ, Hong Z. Inhibitory effects of *Morindaofficinalis* extract on bone loss in ovariectomized rats. *Molecules* 2009; 14: 2049-61.
26. Nisslein T, Freudenstein J. Effects of an isopropanolic extract of *Cimicifugaracemosa* on urinary crosslinks and other parameters of bone quality in an ovariectomized rat model of osteoporosis. *J Bone Miner Metab* 2003; 21: 370-6.
27. Oh KO, Kim SW, Kim JY, *et al.* Effect of *Rehmanniaglutinosa* Libosch extracts on bone metabolism. *ClinChemActa* 2003; 334: 185-95.
28. Potter SM, Baum JA, Teng H, *et al.* Soy protein and isoflavones: their effects on blood lipids and bone density in postmenopausal women. *Am J ClinNutr* 1998; 68: 1375S-9S.
29. Prabhakara RN, M. Lakshmana. *Withaniasomnifera* improves bone calcification in calcium-deficient ovariectomized rats. *Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 2006; 58(4): 513-519.

30. Reddy NP, Lakshmana M., Udupa U.V. "Antiosteoporotic Activity of OST-6, a herb mineral preparation in calcium deficient ovariectomized rats". *Phytother Res* Jan2004; 18(1): 25-9.
31. Rong Z, Shi JH, Chen L, Feng Z, Hong QG, Qi BM. *Achyranthes bidentata* root extract prevent OVX- induced osteoporosis in rats. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 2012; 139(1): 12-18.
32. Ruchi S, Thakur, F.A. Toppo, P.K. Singour, P.K Chaurasiya, Rajesh S, Pawar. Preclinical studies of various extracts of *Polyalthia longifolia* for the management of Dexamethasone induced osteoporosis in rats. *International Journal of pharmacy and Pharmaceutical sciences*, 2013; 5(1): 267-270.
33. Rukshar A, Neha GB. Effects of *Nigella sativa* against osteoporosis. *International Journal of pure and Applied Bioscience*, 2013; 1(2): 6-14.
34. Saleemulla K, Chandresh D, Vinit P, K.K. Srinivasan, A.Srinivasan. Methanol extract of dried exudate of *Commiphora mukul* prevents bone resorption in ovariectomized rats. *Pharmaceutical Biology*, 2012; 50(10): 1330 -1336.
35. Shih CC, Wu YW, Lin WC. Ameliorative effects of *Anoectochilus formosanus* extract on osteopenia in ovariectomized rats. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 2001, 77 (2-3): 233-238.
36. Shirwaikar A, Khan S, Malini S. Antiosteoporotic effect of ethanol extract of *Cissus quadrangularis* Linn. on ovariectomized rat. *J Ethnopharmacol* 2003; 89: 245-50.
37. Shirwaikar, A and Nanda, S and Parmar, V and Khan, Saleemulla. Methanol Extract of the Fruits of *Morinda citrifolia* Linn., Restores Bone Loss in Ovariectomized Rats. *International Journal of Pharmacology*, 2011; 7 (4): 446-454.
38. Shirwaikar A, Prabhu RG, Malini S. Activity of *Wedelia calendulacea* Less. In post-menopausal osteoporosis. *Phytomedicine* 2006; 13: 43-8.
39. Siham M.A. EL Shenwy, Nemat A.Z Yassin, Osama A Badary, Mostafa AN EL-Moneem and Hanam M AL Shafeiy. Study of the effect of *Allium porrum* osteoporosis induced in rats. *Scholar's research library (Der Pharmacia letter)*, 2013, 5(1); 188-198.
40. Srinivasa RS, K Sreedhara RP, Kumar MB. Preventive role of *Emblica officinalis* and *Cissus quadrangularis* on bone loss in osteoporosis. *International journal of pharmacy and pharmaceutical sciences* 2013; 5(4): 465-470.
41. Subhehan, Yusnita R, Mufidah. The characterization and anti-osteoporotic activity of Sappanligum (*caesalpiniasappan L.*) extracts. *International journal of phytomedicine* 2013;5;07-13.
42. Suk NK, Jong SL, Joung HP, Jae HC, Jae HP Kwang KC, Ok HL, Il-suk K. In vitro Anti-osteoporosis properties of diverse Korean *Drynariae rhizome* phenolic extracts. *Nutrients*, 2014; 6: 1737-1751.
43. Tsai MH, Huang GS, Hung YC, Bin L, Liao LT, Lin LW. *Psoralea corylifolia* extract ameliorates experimental osteoporosis in ovariectomized rats. *Am J Chin Med* 2007; 35: 669-80.
44. Wang XX, Wu J, Chiba H, Umegaki K, Yamada K, Ishimi Y. *Puerariae radix* prevents bone loss in ovariectomized mice. *J Bone Miner Metab*, 2003, 21 (5): 268-275.
45. Wang ZL, Sun JY, Wang DN, Xie YH, Wang SW, Zhao WM. Pharmacological studies of the large-scaled purified genistein from Huaijiao (*Sophora japonica* – Leguminosae) on anti-osteoporosis. *Phytomedicine* 2006; 13(9-10): 718-23.

46. Wong MS, Zhang Y, Li XL, *et al.* Anti-osteoporotic effect of *Erythrina variegata L.* in ovariectomized rats. *J Ethnopharmacol* 2007; 109:165-9.
47. Xie F, Wu CF, Lai WP, *et al.* The osteoprotective effect of Herbaepimedii (HEP) extract *in vivo* and *in vitro*. *eCAM* 2005; 2: 353- 61.
48. Yao Xin-Sheng, Fang XIE, Chun-Fu WU, *et al.* Increase in bonemass and bone strength by *Sambucuswilliamsii* HANCE in ovariectomized rats. *Biol Pharm Bull* 2005; 28: 1879-85.
49. Yongzhong Z, Longjiang Y, Mingzhang A, *et al.* Effect of ethanol extract of *Lepidiummeyerii* Walp. on osteoporosis in ovariectomized rat. *J Ethnopharmacol* 2006; 105: 274-9.

DOI:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7233836>

Received: 7 October 2014;

Accepted; 20 November 2014;

Available online : 8 December 2014
